

Tartrate Complex of Calcium

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Tartrate complex of calcium has been studied by pH-titration method. The ionic complex has been found to be of 1:1 type and is formed according to the reaction:

The equilibrium constant of the reaction is determined to be 1.49×10^2 .

Cannan and Kibrick,¹ Schubert and Lindenbaum, and Lakskorin *et al.*² determined the stability constant of calcium tartrate complex by other methods and found it to be 63.10, 60.26, and 63.10 respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

A calcium perchlorate solution ($M/10$) was prepared according to Patnaik and Pani⁴.

Expt. 1.—Curve A of Fig. 1 represents the results obtained by the pH titration of 120 ml of a solution containing 0.01 g. mole of tartatic acid and 0.01 g. mole of sodium perchlorate and curve B, that of the same volume of another solution containing 0.01 g. mole of tartaric acid, 0.01 g. mole of sodium perchlorate, and 0.001 g. mole of calcium perchlorate against $N/2$ -NaOH solution at 37°.

Expt. 2.—Curve A of Fig 2 represents the results obtained by the pH titration of 100 ml of a solution containing 0.01 g. mole of sodium perchlorate and curve B, that of another solution of same volume containing 0.01 g. mole of sodium perchlorate and 0.001 g. mole of calcium perchlorate against 0.01 M sodium tartrate at 38°.

DISCUSSION

In experiments 1 and 2, the low pH in the system B may be due to removal of the tartrate ligand from the solution by calcium due to complex formation.

In expt. 1, the amount of tartaric acid, compared to the calcium content, is large and proton is not liberated during the reaction; the horizontal distance between the curves

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2314.

2. *Ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 3529.

3. *Atomic energy E. S. S. R.*, 1950, **7**, 110.

4. *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 220.

indicates the amount of tartrate ligand bound due to complex formation. Let x and y be the two points on the same pH axis on the curves A and B, respectively. If $[T]_x$, $[T]_y$, and $[Ca(ClO_4)_2]$ represent the molar concentration of total tartrate at x , total tartrate and calcium perchlorate at y , respectively, then the number of ligands bound per metal ion ($\bar{n}$) can be expressed as

$$\bar{n} = \frac{[T]_x - [T]_y}{[Ca(ClO_4)_2]}$$

$\bar{n}$ was calculated and found to be 0.374, 0.360, 0.355, and 0.276 at pH 3.63, 3.75, 3.87, and 4.28, respectively. The existence of any other complex besides 1:1 type is not indicated.

$N/2$ -NaOH added (ml).

FIG. 1

0.1M-Na tartrate added (ml).

FIG. 2

In Expt. 2, the added tartrate ions are partially bound to the calcium due to complex formation, as a result of which the pH does not rise as rapidly as observed in the system A. The break in the curve after addition of very nearly 1 g. mole of sodium tartrate per g. mole of calcium perchlorate indicates the formation of a 1:1 type complex. By proceeding in the manner, as described in the calcium citrate system⁴, it can be shown that

$$[T^{2-}] = [T]_A$$

$$[CaT] = [T]_B - [T]_A$$

$$[Ca^{2+}] = [Ca(ClO_4)_2] - [CaT]$$

(where $[T]_A$ and $[T]_B$ denote, respectively, the molar concentration of tartrate at the points A and B). $[T^{2-}]$, $[CaT]$ and $[Ca^{2+}]$ were calculated as before⁴.

The equilibrium constant of the reaction:

was calculated and the values are recorded in Table I. The mean value of the equilibrium constant is found to be 1.49×10^2 .

TABLE I

pH.	$[T^{2-}] \times 10^3$.	$[T]_B \times 10^3$.	$[Ca(ClO_4)_2] \times 10^2$.	$[CaT] \times 10^3$.	$[Ca^{2+}] \times 10^3$.	$K \times 10^{-2}$.
6.79	1.865	3.857	1.058	1.982	8.598	1.24
6.91	2.724	5.861	1.038	2.937	7.443	1.45
6.96	3.383	6.977	1.023	3.594	6.636	1.61
7.00	3.847	7.834	1.014	3.987	6.153	1.68
7.10	4.943	10.720	0.982	5.777	4.045	1.49

Thanks are due to Prof. S. Pani of U. C. E., Burla, for his kind interest and encouragement.

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Received August 17, 1964.